

Beyond borders and beyond numbers: purposeful engagement in large engineering classes in a joint international college

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Abstract

Large classes of over 100 students are common in international programmes, but maintaining attendance, participation and meaningful engagement remain challenging. This paper reflects on teaching practice in Chang'an-Dublin International College (CDIC) delivering engineering modules to Chinese students. Across Stage 2 to 4 modules, several practical strategies were implemented, i.e., low-stakes surprise quizzes to encourage preparation and attendance, adjustments to continuous assessment, self-organising team agreements to support responsibility in large group projects, and structured oral and written group presentations to promote active participation. In addition, the group work approach incorporated a mid-semester draft submission followed by structured peer-review between groups, enabling students to practise giving and receiving feedback and to benchmark their work against peers. To address uneven contribution in large teams, an end-of-module individual self-evaluation (and evaluation of teammates) was used to flag clear cases of non-participation and to support fairer grade adjustments where needed. Together, these low-disruption measures were introduced without major changes to module structure and are presented as transferable options for lecturers working in large engineering classrooms where confidence to participate can vary across students. Based on observations, the paper argues that engagement in large classes depends less on size and more on pedagogical design.

Keywords: *Large classes; engineering education; student engagement; attendance; group work; generative AI.*

1. Introduction

Traditionally, lectures and tutorials have been the dominant forms of instruction in conventional face-to-face undergraduate courses (Nyamapfene, 2010). With the expansion of higher education systems and increasing student numbers, these lecture-based formats are frequently delivered to large cohorts of students. In many universities, particularly in engineering programmes, lectures often take place in large classrooms where cohorts may exceed one hundred students. Hence, large-class lectures are extremely common in mass education around the world and lack of attendance is a regular topic of discussion (Basken, 2023; Williams, 2022). Many lecturers and researchers have explored pedagogical approaches aimed at increasing participation and improving engagement within large lecture settings. These active learning interventions varied widely in intensity and implementation and included approaches as diverse as occasional group problem-solving, worksheets or tutorials completed during class, use of personal response systems with or without peer instruction, and studio or workshop course designs (Freeman et al., 2014).

Despite these developments, maintaining regular attendance and active participation remains a practical concern in many large engineering classes. In technical subjects where concepts build progressively across lectures, missing sessions may make subsequent material more difficult to follow, which can further reduce engagement over time. These challenges are also present in international engineering programmes delivered in English, where students may have different levels of confidence when asking questions or contributing to classroom discussions.

This paper reflects on teaching practice in large undergraduate engineering modules delivered at Chang'an-Dublin International College (CDIC). In this context, several practical strategies were gradually introduced within normal classroom practice to support attendance, preparation, and participation. These included short low-stakes quizzes during lectures, team agreements to structure collaboration in group projects, peer-review feedback between groups, structured oral presentations, and individual self-evaluations of team contribution.

Rather than presenting a controlled experimental study, the purpose of this paper is to describe these teaching practices and to reflect on how relatively small adjustments within existing module structures may help support student engagement in large engineering cohorts.

2. Description of the Teaching/Learning Context

The teaching discussed in this paper takes place at CDIC, founded in 2020, which is a joint international education partnership between University College Dublin (UCD) and

Chang'an University (CHU) in Xi'an, China (University College Dublin 2020). The lecturing is divided among faculty members from UCD and CHU, with UCD staff delivering several engineering modules to undergraduate students across Stage 2 to Stage 4 of the programme. On the other hand, modules on Stage 1 are fully handled by CHU. During Stages 1 and 2, students take English language modules aimed at reinforcing their language skills. Nonetheless, the English proficiency of students can significantly vary within the same cohort. Class sizes are typically large, exceeding 100 students. Each UCD staff member typically handles three modules in which they are the sole lecturer. Support from teaching assistants is available for in-class activities or grading. The number of components varies from module to module, but assessment generally combines continuous assessment activities (group work, short quizzes, tutorials, etc.) and an end-of-semester exam.

3. Literature Review

Nowadays, large classes are a common part of higher education, but they often make it harder for lecturers to build interaction, maintain attendance and support meaningful participation (Mulryan-Kyne, 2010). Freeman et al. (2014) showed that active learning improves student performance in science, engineering and mathematics, which supports the idea that large engineering lectures should include structured activities rather than relying only on traditional delivery. Attendance is also important. Credé et al. (2010) found a clear relationship between class attendance and academic achievement, and Nyamapfene (2010) reported a similar concern in engineering education. Farrell and Logan (2022) argued that developing a sense of community in a large class requires deliberate teaching design, as student numbers can weaken teacher-student and student-student relationships. Felten and Farrell (2024) extended this idea through “relationship-rich education at scale”, which suggests that even large enrolment classes can support learning and wellbeing when instructors intentionally create opportunities for connection, belonging and interaction. Peer feedback is another important element. Carless and Boud (2018) defined student feedback literacy as the ability to understand, judge and use feedback to improve learning. Boud and Soler (2016) also argued that assessment should support learning beyond a single module, which is relevant to the use of draft submissions, peer review and revision in group projects. Similarly, Boud et al. (2014)'s work on peer learning supports the value of students learning from and with one another, especially when peer interaction is formally built into the assessment process. Also, Burke-Hayes (2021) described peer review as a way to enhance students' feedback literacy in large classes. The group work and oral presentation are the next elements that should be considered in large classes. For example, Murphy and Winkler (2023) discussed the problem of managing group project work and “free-rider” behaviour in large classes, and Buckley (2024) examined interactive oral

assessment in large postgraduate education programmes and linked oral assessment with academic integrity and student engagement.

4. Practical Strategies to Support Engagement in Large Engineering Classes

In general, students in CDIC are committed to their studies, but sometimes attendance and active participation can be challenging in large lecture settings. Additionally, students have different levels of confidence when asking questions or contributing during class discussions, particularly in technical subjects delivered in English. Over time, it became clear that maintaining attendance and participation in this context required some practical adjustments in day-to-day teaching. Rather than making major changes to the module structure, several approaches were introduced within normal classroom practice. These changes were mainly aimed at encouraging students to come prepared and to stay involved during lectures and group activities. Gradually, a positive change could be observed in the classroom atmosphere, with students attending more regularly and engaging more actively during sessions.

4.1. Surprise Quizzes to Support Attendance and Preparation

A comprehensive meta-analysis of class attendance in higher education demonstrated a strong positive relationship between attendance and academic performance (Credé et al., 2010). In the same direction, attendance in Stage 4 engineering modules at CDIC became a concern during the trimester. In large lecture classes, students sometimes rely on lecture slides or notes shared among classmates and may feel that missing a session does not have a strong impact. In engineering subjects, however, topics are closely connected and missing classes can make later material harder to follow (Delavande et al., 2025; Dwyer, 2011; Nyamapfene, 2010).

To encourage more regular attendance, short quizzes were occasionally introduced during lectures (see Figure 1). Although Figure 1 shows only part of the classroom during one quiz session, the overall module cohort consisted of more than 100 students. These quizzes were brief and focused only on material recently discussed in class. They were not intended as formal assessments but rather as a reminder for students to keep up with weekly content. After some time, attendance began to stabilise and students appeared more engaged during lectures. The quizzes also helped identify topics that required further explanation, which was useful for adjusting teaching in subsequent sessions.

Figure 1. Quiz: a solution to good class attendance (Gordan 2024)

4.2. Large Group Projects: Team Agreements, Peer-Review Feedback, Structured Group Presentations, and Self-Evaluations

Group projects form an important part of engineering education. In the context of large classes, they also have the practical benefit for the lecturer of effectively reducing the assessment load. In this section, the setup for a semester-long group work in Transportation Engineering is discussed. The implemented assessment strategy comprises several steps, as indicated in Figure 2 below. Four main elements will be explored here, namely the team agreement (Step 2), the peer review process (Step 4), the oral presentations (step 7) and the self-evaluation of team members that takes places at the end of the process (not shown in Figure 2). This group work approach has a direct impact in the context of large classes since it allows providing detailed feedback for each piece of work, which is not logistically possible in case of individual assignments in large groups. Although each piece of work corresponds to a group and not to a single learner, ideally it would have been produced by the collective effort of the group, hence implying that each individual would benefit from the feedback. Nonetheless, ensuring that all students actively contribute to their group remains a challenge. In addition, the proposed framework tries to incorporate multisource

feedback, which is recognised in the literature as having potential benefits for students in large classes (Black et al., 2021).

Figure 2. Implemented assessment strategy

Managing teamwork within large classes can sometimes be difficult. In some cases, differences in contribution between group members can affect both learning experience and project outcomes. Team agreements are one way in which this challenge is addressed. At the start of the semester, students were asked to prepare simple team agreements at the beginning of their projects. Figure 3 shows the agreement form sample. Each group discussed how they intended to organise communication, divide tasks and manage deadlines. Rather than providing strict rules, students were encouraged to agree on expectations themselves. This small step appeared to help groups organise their work more effectively. Students often referred to their agreements when difficulties occurred, which reduced the need for frequent intervention from teaching staff. It also encouraged a greater sense of shared responsibility within teams.

Following the signature of the team agreement, each group had several weeks to work on their report. Halfway through the semester, students submitted a draft version of their work. This is intended to be a substantially developed work including the necessary sections and references. However, the main goal of asking for this draft at an early stage is that other groups can provide feedback. Each group is randomly assigned another group for which they will act as reviewers. In return, the work from each group is reviewed by a different one. The purpose of this activity is twofold. On the one hand, it allows students to see how other groups are developing their work. This can be beneficial and help them identify areas

of improvement. In addition, this activity introduces students to peer-review feedback practices and provides them with an opportunity to develop critical thinking skills.

After receiving the feedback from their peers, complemented by feedback from the instructor, the groups work on their report for the remainder of the semester, resulting in the submission of the final report and a set of slides for their oral presentation. The purpose of having an oral presentation is to help students develop soft skills, but also, they need to answer questions about their work and show a deep understanding of the implemented concepts. Each group is given 10-12 minutes for their presentation, followed by queries from the instructor and their peers. The order of presentation was randomised so that students did not know when their turn will take place. This can help ensuring that students attend the presentations from other groups and that they do not ask pre-arranged questions to other groups. In terms of logistics, the presentations were split over four different sessions to ensure that enough time was available for each group, i.e., 5 or 6 groups per session. Students were notified in advance so that they would attend all four sessions, even if the randomised order meant they did not know which specific day they would present. The challenge of splitting the presentations across several sessions was that groups that had presented early were more likely to skip the later sessions.

Group Number:

Group Members: [All Names]

Agreement:

1. **Group Meetings:** We agree to meet [frequency] (e.g., weekly, bi-weekly) at [time] on [day(s)] to discuss our progress, assign tasks, and address any issues.
2. **Communication:** We will maintain open and effective communication within our group. We will use [communication tools] (e.g., email, messaging apps, shared documents) to stay connected and share updates.
3. **Work Division:** We will divide the workload among group members based on individual strengths, interests, and availability. We will ensure that all members contribute equally to the project.
4. **Deadlines:** We will set clear deadlines for completing individual tasks and group deliverables.
5. **Accountability:** If a group member is not contributing to the project, we will address the issue directly and respectfully.
6. **Conflict Resolution:** We agree to resolve conflicts peacefully and constructively through open communication and compromise.
7. **Decision-Making:** We will make decisions as a group, taking into account the input and perspectives of all members.

By signing this agreement, we agree to abide by these terms and work collaboratively to achieve our project goals.

Signatures: [All members]

Date:

Figure 3. Agreement form sample

Finally, a final piece of self-assessment is included to again address some of the challenges mentioned at the start of this section. This is an individual activity in which each student assigns a score to their own performance and that of their teammates from 1 to 10. Although this may be an imperfect tool, e.g., some students just give a score of 10 to everyone, or some may give higher scores to friends regardless of their performance; it can be useful in identifying clear cases in which individual students have not significantly contributed to the group work during the semester. Table 1 below provides an anonymised example of this kind of evaluation. Each row represents the score given by one student. If the scores provided by Student D are omitted, a pattern can be seen in which Students E and F are consistently getting higher scores from everyone, whereas the other group members score a bit lower. This tool can be used to fine-tune the final grade awarded to the students at the end of the semester-long assignment. In the current implementation of the self-assessment tool, students are not provided with specific criteria but rather general instructions to evaluate their performance. However, in future implementations, it would be desirable to establish specific criteria to guide the students in their self-evaluation.

Table 1. Self-evaluation matrix.

	Student A	Student B	Student C	Student D	Student E	Student F
Student A	10	8	10	10	10	8
Student B	7	7	8	9	9	7
Student C	8	8	8	9	10	7
Student D	10	10	10	10	10	10
Student E	5	4	8	9	9	4
Student F	8	8	9	9	9	8

Source: Authors' owns work

4.3. Increased Continuous Assessment and the Integration of Emerging Topics

Some of the traditional UCD modules within the CDIC programme used to include very high-stakes final-exam contributions to the final grade. Bridge Engineering is among those examples which originally had a 90% final exam weight. The remaining 10% was made up of continuous assessment, with a minor impact on the final grade. Attendance problems were evident, similar to the observations above, and one major change was to bring the continuous assessment weight to 50%, aiming to enable I) distributed responsibility and accountability over the trimester, II) guided and timely checkpoints recapping the module fundamentals, III) opportunities for progress monitoring and pre-exam feedback.

Apart from the examination strategies, emerging developments in today's world are also incorporated into the module delivery strategies while maintaining the core teaching and learning content. As part of a trans-university and transnational study, generative artificial

intelligence (genAI) technologies were integrated into classroom activities, e.g., two-session exercises covering AI's I) introduction, II) ethics, III) limitations, and IV) in-class implementations within the Bridge Engineering module (Leahy et al., 2025). Leahy et al. (2025) investigated how these exercises support classroom engagement through surveys and have shown that AI implementations within the modules improved I) engagement with peers, II) engagement with the module coordinator, and III) engagement with the course subjects.

In summary, if implemented, advancements in digital technologies can prompt innovative class activities that contribute directly to engagement and indirectly to attendance. Those innovative approaches can be further paired with continuous assessment strategies to drive student interest over the trimester and maintain a dynamic environment with many opportunities for interaction between students and the module coordinator.

5. Reflection and Implications for Practice

Experience across CDIC modules suggests that the challenges often associated with large classes are not only related to student numbers. In many cases, small adjustments in teaching practice can influence how students respond during lectures and collaborative activities. The introduction of short quizzes supported attendance and preparation, while team agreements helped improve group organisation. Structured presentations also created opportunities for students to articulate their understanding of technical concepts and respond to questions from both the teacher and their peers. Peer-review and self-assessment tools can help students develop critical thinking and reflect on their own work. In large classes, this type of structured interaction can help shift the classroom atmosphere from passive listening towards more active participation.

Another observation from these modules is that relatively simple organisational tools can play a useful role in supporting collaboration in large student groups. The introduction of team agreements encouraged students to clarify expectations at the beginning of a project, while peer-review activities created opportunities for groups to reflect on the quality of their work and compare it with that of others. In addition, the use of individual self-evaluation at the end of the project provided a practical way to identify clear cases where contributions within teams were uneven. None of these approaches required major changes to module design, but together they contributed to a more active classroom environment.

6. Conclusion

Large lecture classes are a common feature of current higher education systems, particularly in engineering programmes with growing student cohorts. While such environments are often associated with reduced participation and limited interaction, the experience described in this paper suggests that student engagement in large classrooms is influenced not only by class size but also by the organisation of teaching activities within the module. Drawing on teaching practice at CDIC, this paper presented a set of practical approaches implemented within regular classroom teaching.

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